

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

Deliverable D7.2

PARC FAIR Data Policy (PFDP)

WP7 Task 7.1

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Abbreviations

AGA = Annotated Grant Agreement

AI = Artificial Intelligence

CA = Consortium Agreement

DMP = Data Management Plan

FAIR = Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable

GA = Grant Agreement

GSB = Grant Signatory Board

ML = Machine Learning

MB = Management Board

PARC = Partnership for Assessment of the Risks of Chemicals

PFDP = PARC FAIR Data Policy

WP = Work Package

RA = Risk Assessment

Document History

Version	Date	Reviewer name/Institutions	Short description of changes
0.1	October 6-7, 2022	WP7.1 Members at Brno meeting	Creation of first list of topics to be addressed.
0.2	February 15, 2023	WP7.1 Writing group	Manual extraction of stakeholder topics to build list of topics. Consolidated list of topics and first draft of statements & text. With textual snippets from GA, CA and AGA.
0.2	March 2, 2023	WP7.1 Writing group, plus Barbara Magagna, Erik Schultes, Sylvie Remy, Iseult Lynch, Jan Theunis	Review first version.
1.0	March 16, 2023	WP7.1 Writing group, plus Barbara Magagna, Erik Schultes, Sylvie Remy, Iseult Lynch, Jan Theunis. Followed by Final check Version 1.0 with input from WP7.1 all participants (TNO (NL), UOB (UK). Partners: ANSES (FR), BRGM (FR), VITO (BE), MU(CZ), UZIS (CZ), UBA (DE), ISS (IT), KWR (NL), UL-LACDR (NL), NIVA (N), UG-PL (PL), JSI (SI), KI (SE), AUTH (EL), NIPH, UH Sub-contractors: GFF (BE).)	Content of previous version migrated to PARC EU format.
1.0	March 20, 2023	V1 version send to MB on 20-03-23: PARC_D7.2 FAIR Data Policy V1_20220320.pdf Derived from PARC_D71_FAIR_Data_Policy_V1_20220320.docx (version 3.0 Sharepoint history) Stored under VITO Sharepoint as: PARC_D71_FAIR_Data_Policy_V1_20220320 version for PDF V1.0 for ANSES SHAREPOINT.docx	version send to MB
onward process executed since V1.0:			

<p><01-04-2023</p>	<p>Final dates selected for 2 x three online Teams consultation sessions to gather input from the PARC community and discuss topics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PARC_PFD: Data governance / Management of sensitive data: TEAMS session #1 Wednesday May 10th 10.00-12.00 CEST • PARC_PFD: Open data, (including Embargo/release/open data) / Data quality: TEAMS Session #2 Friday May 12th 14.00-16.00 CEST • PARC_PFD: FAIR data: ambitions and levels of FAIRness, implementation roadmaps / OTHER: TEAMS Session #3 Monday May 22th 10.00-12.00 CEST • PARC_PFD: Data governance / Management of sensitive data: TEAMS session #4 Tuesday May 30th 15.00-17.00 CEST • PARC_PFD: Open data, (including Embargo/release/open data) / Data quality: TEAMS session #5 Monday June 5th 10.00-12.00 CEST • PARC_PFD: ambitions and levels of FAIRness, implementation roadmaps / OTHER: TEAMS session #6 Tuesday June 6th 15.00-17.00 CEST <p>Invited were: PARC Task Leaders, project Leaders, Data Champions, Data Liaisons, MB/GSB, ECHA, EFSA, JRC (IPCHEM), Data protection and Ethics Board, National Hub coordinating Team.</p>
<p>03-04-2023</p>	<p>The PFD V1 was announced during the Management Board Meeting. Online (Teams) consultation sessions (discussion topics and dates) announced. Announcement of the proposed review and consultation process (outlined here). Ask for approval of discussion topics or additional topics if needed. Note: the MB was informed on this after the actual Management Board Meeting.</p>
<p>25-04-2023</p>	<p>Distribution of e-mails to the PARC target group with invitations for Online (Teams) consultation sessions and link to a Teams form : PFD collection of responses.url to gather additional input when participants are not able to join an online session. The emails were sent to the following target group:</p> <p>PARC Task Leaders; Parc Project Leaders; Data Champions; Data Liaisons; MB/GSB, plus ECHA, EFSA,; JRC (IPCHEM); The Data protection and Ethics Board; The National Hub coordinating Team</p> <p>Until 06-06-2023, the PARC target group was enabled to attend of the 6 online (Teams) consultation sessions and to provide input via the TEAMS forms.</p> <p>Ultimately attendance was by representatives from academia, research institutes, decentralized agencies, national /public health agencies etc.. The number of participants attending the online Teams sessions varied between 30 and 55. Across all 6 TEAMS sessions, 154 unique individuals present in any of the telcons/332 individuals invited: 46,3 %. (9.9% of the total PARC community).</p>
<p>< 24-06-2023</p>	<p>Revision of version 1.0 to 1.1, using the Teams session input and online comments to the TEAM form was completed by Fred van de Brug and Rob Stierum (TNO)</p>
<p>26-06-2023</p>	<p>V1.1 version send to MB by e-mail on 26-06-23: PARC_D7.2_FAIR_Data_Policy_V1.1_26-06-2023.pdf stored under VITO Sharepoint as:</p>

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	<p>https://vitoresearch.sharepoint.com/:w:/r/sites/parc-wp7/_layouts/15/Doc.aspx?sourcedoc=%7Bc0f98944-cbac-461e-948d-28d22587e739%7D&action=edit&wdPid=44ca977b</p> <p>The PFDP V1.1 was approved by the PARC Management Board (MB) and Grant Signatory Board (GSB) and was taken into effect from 01-07-2023.</p>
28-9-2023	<p>MB approved the reviewers not involved in drafting V1.1, but towards PARC_D7.2_FAIR_Data_Policy_V2_010923 Martine Bakker (RIVM) Susana Loureiro (UAVR)</p> <p>The comments were reviewed and addressed by Rob Stierum and Fred van de Brug (TNO) toward the final deliverable PARC_D7.2_FAIR_Data_Policy_V2_280923_FINAL.</p>
17-10-2023	<p>Submission of PARC_D7.2_FAIR_Data_Policy_V2_171023_FINAL.pdf to ANSES PARC CT</p>
20-10-2023	<p>Submission to the EU portal has been done by ANSES PARC CT.</p>

Abstract

This PARC Fair Data Policy (PFDP) defines the high level principles and conditions that govern provision, management, access, use and re-use of PARC data (both generated in projects and re-used from other sources), in line with the FAIR principles and the PARC Initial Data Management Plan (DMP) (D7.1), while taking into account legal aspects (i.e., GDPR), security, transparency, sustainability and quality of the data used and generated in PARC. It also highlights the roles and responsibilities of WP7 (as the FAIR data work package) and the data generating WPs (WP4-6 and WP8) and their respective projects.

The Grant Agreement (GA) declares that "In line with Article 8.6 of the Consortium Agreement, **each participant of PARC will be required to comply with the PARC FAIR Data Policy**", meaning that all partners must be aware of, and agree with, the contents of the PARC FAIR data policy. To achieve this awareness and consensus, a dedicated communication and consultation strategy was a core aspect of the development of the PARC FAIR data policy, alongside review of a wide range of background documents and related policies from partner and regulatory agencies.

The topics contained in this PFDP were selected from a list of topics which were mentioned by PARC partners and key PARC stakeholders. The topics were derived from reading various data policies / other data documents which were found on the websites of relevant stakeholders / organisations. The derived hierarchical structure of topics was taken as the backbone for this PFDP document. For each of the topics, text was added on the basis of the Consortium Agreement (CA), Grant Agreement (GA) / Annotated Grant Agreement (AGA). Additional input was retrieved from a series of online MS Teams session for the PARC community (PARC Task Leaders; PARC Project Leaders; Data Champions; Data Liaisons; Management Board (MB) and Governance Steering Board (GSB), plus ECHA, EFSA, JRC (IPCHEM); The Data protection and Ethics Board; The National Hub coordinating Team) and the PARC partners and stakeholder policy documents.

The operationalisation of the PFDP has three important pillars. Firstly, the overarching WP 7 deliverable D7.1 Initial DMP. Additionally, the PARC project-level DMPs which must align with the overarching PARC DMP and the PFDP. Lastly, the actual FAIRification of data which is supported by data champions, data liaisons and the FAIR implementation taskgroup.

This version (V2) of the PARC FAIR Data Policy, with deliverable due date M18, has been approved by Management Board (MB)/ Grant Signatory Board (GSB) and takes effect from 01-07-2023.

Keywords

PARC, Data policy, Data management plan, DMP, FAIR, FAIRification, Stakeholders, Risk assessment

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1. Introduction

Although the access to regulatory information on chemicals (e.g., environmental occurrence, exposure patterns and toxicological properties) has improved considerably, e.g., through REACH or EFSA's new open access platform (<https://open.efsa.europa.eu/>) including a code, data and other scientific materials repository at Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/communities/efsa-kj/about/>), risk assessment agencies and regulatory bodies, at the EU and Member state level, find themselves confronted with gaps in knowledge or seemingly conflicting results, and the gap between scientific progress and regulation remains wide. One of the aims of PARC is to enable all of the scientific communities involved in chemical risk assessment, as well as risk managers and stakeholders, to have access to high-quality data by facilitating data findability, accessibility, interoperability and re-use (FAIR) both for research and regulatory risk assessment (from the PARC –Description of Action (Technical description) Part B)). In order to facilitate this, a PARC Fair Data Policy (PFDP) needs to be put into place, and implemented by all PARC partners, which is outlined and presented in this document.

As described in the PARC Grant Agreement (GA) and the PARC Consortium Agreement (CA), work package (WP)7 is responsible for the generation of the PFDP, including the creation of guiding principles and the overarching PARC Data Management Plan (DMP, deliverable D7.1), which outlines the more practical implementation and ensures connectivity to the ethics and data protection framework.

This PFDP is not intended as a practical operational document to help PARC in data management, which is within the DMP and project specific DMPs, but instead provides guiding principles on a.o.: aim and scope of PFDP, applicable laws and frameworks; data governance and management, including security, quality; transparency and openness; FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) including the foreseen ambition of PARC to which extent FAIR can be accomplished throughout PARC; intellectual property and sensitive personal data. This will be explained in more detail in the next Chapters.

Based on the PFDP, WP7 will set up specific methods and tools and guidance to enable partners to FAIRify their data and facilitate data reuse within the research and innovation (R&I) WPs of PARC, by regulatory agencies and for research outside the scope of PARC by the broader scientific community. In detail, this operationalisation of the PFDP has three important pillars:

First, the overarching WP 7 deliverable D7.1, the Initial DMP, describes the preferred choices and considerations on how to implement the policy and is a living document that will be updated throughout the PARC project. Increasingly, the overarching DMP will refer to the tools and practical guidance provided by WP7, via the inclusion of hyperlinks. These links will involve a final selection of an online DMP resource to be used by PARC projects together with the tools and guidelines for FAIRification, in direct relation to the next two pillars

Secondly, the PARC project-level DMPs will be aligned with this overarching PARC DMP, via a.o. the use of an online DMP resources. The compliance for this will be overseen by the PARC Data Champions (WP-specific) and Data Liaisons (from WP7).

Lastly, the actual FAIRification of data is further supported by data champions, data liaisons and the FAIR implementation taskgroup. The roles and the required training are being described in more detail in the DMP (WP 7 deliverable D7.1) and are operationalised within WP 7. WP7 is also developing the tools and workflows to support PARC partners in the actual FAIRification of their data, to support operationalisation of the PFDP. (see also Figure 1). These tools will be referenced from the overarching DMP and publicly available online and in public software repositories like GitHub.

The DMP (and PFDP) will become increasingly detailed and prescriptive as PARC progresses.

As contained within the Grant Agreement, and in line with Article 8.6 of the Consortium Agreement, **“each Participant (Entities participating in the action as beneficiaries, affiliated entities, associated partners, third parties giving in-kind contributions, subcontractors or recipients of financial support to third parties) of PARC will be required to comply with the PARC FAIR Data Policy, the DMP, and the ethics and data protection framework. This effectively means that PARC Participants need to actively contribute and familiarize themselves with the PFDP policy principles, act accordingly, implement it in their way of working and feel responsible for FAIRification of their work, as this will facilitate the reuse of data created within PARC for development of future risk assessment purposes.”** Throughout this

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PFDP, we use the terms Researchers and Participants interchangeably as “Researchers/Participants”, with “researchers” meaning individual researchers close to data generation/curation, **including PARC project leads**, for which this PFDP will be a guiding document, and “Participants” is used whenever we need to refer in the policy to a more legal definition (e.g., in reference to the Consortium Agreement and Grant Agreement).

The PFDP and DMP are deliverables in the PARC work plan. As described under the WP7 description in the General Agreement (GA): “The PFDP (and the DMP) will be updated regularly”. The first version of the PFDP will be formally delivered in M18 (October 2023), with release dates of updates not specified. The Initial PARC DMP (D7.1, delivered at M6) will be updated with formal deliverables in M42 and M72. The PFDP updates will be available through the “[Partnership Handbook](#)”, which will be continuously updated and distributed to all partners for good operating procedures, including guidelines, templates and summary of the Consortium Agreement rules. All Participants shall respect the requirements set out in these documents and in the ethics and data protection framework, which will be elaborated in a coordinated fashion with WP7 which will be continuously updated and distributed to all partners for good operating procedures, including guidelines, templates and summary of the Consortium Agreement rules.

The PFDP V1.1, (PARC_D7.2_FAIR_Data_Policy_V1.1_20230623.pdf), as presented in the previous Deliverable Report, has been approved by the PARC Management Board (MB) and Governance and Steering Board (GSB) and takes effect from 01-07-2023.

This report represents V2, the final version of the deliverable, taking effect as of 1-11-2023.

2. Explanation of the process of creating the PARC FAIR Data Policy

This initial PFDP has been created following the consultative process outlined in detail in the history of this document, above. Firstly, the topics contained in this PFDP were derived by reading various data policies/other data documents which were found on the websites of several relevant stakeholder organisations. These stakeholders were selected for relevance to enable the widest possible coverage of the different topics of potential relevance for the PFDP and included stakeholders from the risk assessment domain, FAIR data domains, international organisations, academics and publishers.

The resources from which information was extracted are listed in section 14. The information extracted were the topics along with relevant snippets of text in order to understand the context. Stakeholders were:

- co-programmed European Partnership (EOSC)
- EU Decentralized Agency (ECHA, EEA, EFSA)
- EU Project (EU FAIRSFAIR)
- European Commission (EC, Horizon Europe, IPCHEM)
- European Commission/EU Directorate general (COPCSD, JRC)
- International Organisation (with members at country level) (OECD, Science Europe, Unesco)
- Non-Profit Partnership to ensure a permanent open scholarly communication infrastructure to support European research (OpenAIRE, Zenodo)
- Publisher (PLOS, as one of first not for profit publishers fostering the publication of open-access scientific articles in the biological sciences)
- Scientific community initiative (GO FAIR)
- University (University of Edinburgh, as this university spearheaded the development of DMP online, and Utrecht University, as a highly ranked university creating data in the areas of toxicology, risk assessment, exposome research, human clinical data and codeveloped the data sharing system YODA/iRODS etc.)

From these topics and relevant snippets of text, a hierarchical structure of terms and higher level terms was used as the backbone of this document. These are described in Section 3 and onwards, where in the text below terms are used like “aligned with”, this can also be understood as “inspired by”, cross referencing to the original sources.

In addition to the above, topic definitions retrieved from stakeholders directly (where the topics were derived from) and/or other international literature sources (FAIR communities, WIPO, CODATA, OECD, ELIXIR) served as additional input.

3. Aim and scope of the PARC FAIR Data Policy

Aim of the PARC FAIR Data Policy

PARC promotes the harmonisation of data and the exchange of data between different actors (scientific community, health agencies, regulators, policy-makers etc.) and disciplines (exposure science, toxicology, analytical chemistry etc.) to foster transparency and support risk assessment. In order to give direction to this process, the PFDP defines the principles and conditions which PARC Participants are required to apply when producing and using data within PARC.

This PFDP defines the principles and conditions that govern provision, management, access, use and re-use of data, ensure data and associated information is FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable), while taking into account legal and ethical aspects (i.e., data privacy via the GDPR directive), security, transparency, sustainability and quality of the data used and generated in PARC. The PFDP also seeks to safeguard PARC data assets from vendor lock in, be it accidental or intentional (<https://www.gofair.foundation/criteria>).

The PARC Grant Agreement defines FAIR and open data sharing according to the ‘**as open as possible, as closed as necessary**’, effectively “**open by default, unless....**”, principle, which will be the default for PARC. Apart from **data** it includes reports, software, guidelines, method descriptions, formats, templates, semantic artefacts (ontologies, vocabularies etc.).

Scope of the PARC FAIR Data Policy

The PFDP applies to all **data** generated and used in PARC. More in general, all PARC outputs should be made FAIR and published / deposited in open archives as Open Access unless there is a risk of revealing personal data. As PARC is a public initiative not involving companies, it is not expected that confidential business information will impede the FAIRification of (meta)data.

The PARC Open Science Principles as stated in the Grant Agreement have a wider scope than this PFDP, and address **all research objects**. As such, data are part of “all research outputs” (see under “Aim of the PARC FAIR Data Policy” above) but not, as the default, vice versa. So, this PFDP is not concerned with other research outputs (e.g. reports, software, guidelines, method descriptions, formats, templates, semantic artefacts (ontologies, vocabularies etc.)) .

As stated in the PARC Grant Agreement, “the PFDP will define the principles and conditions that govern provision, management, access, use and re-use of **data**, in line with the FAIR principles, while taking into account legal aspects (i.e., GPDR), security, transparency, sustainability and quality of the data. WP7 will provide the framework (guiding principles, data policy, overarching DMP), set up specific methods and tools and guidance to enable Participants / Researchers to FAIRify data and facilitate data reuse in the R&I WPs, in regulatory agencies and beyond PARC.”

The PFDP specifically addresses the scientific and regulatory **data** related aspects of the FAIR and open data sharing statement, in order to define the principles and conditions for the management and use of **data and its accompanying rich metadata** (hereafter referred to as (meta)data) produced and used in PARC. This PFDP adopts the CODATA definition of data: “Facts, measurements, recordings, records, or observations about the world collected by scientists and others, with a minimum of contextual interpretation” (based upon the CODATA Research Data Management Terminology - See Definition of Terms used in the PFDP reproduced within Box 1 for the full definition). Metadata are data that describe data. They provide context and facilitate understanding of what the data are and what they were generated for as also shown in Box 1.

Further, in order to describe the context of the scientific data, the metadata (as defined in Box 1: on, e.g., method descriptions, assay details including for example, any OECD Test Guidelines or Standard Operating Procedures utilised to generate the data, documentation for the dataset, tools/software used to generate or interpret the primary data, quality assurance procedures implemented, as well as e.g., the final publication bibliographic information) must be provided in the FAIRification process of the scientific data. The richness of the metadata and the minimum set of metadata required to enable re-use, are usually agreed through a consensus building processes and are being dealt with in the context of project specific DMPs, facilitation of which is part of the role of PARC WP7.

The FAIRification *per se* of unstructured data (free text, reports separately from the underlying data, protocols, guidelines, publications), **that are not associated with PARC project related scientific data**, is not covered under this PFDP.

Box 1: Definitions of data and metadata as used in the PARC FAIR Data Policy

Data

Facts, measurements, recordings, records, or observations about the world collected by scientists and others, with a minimum of contextual interpretation. Data may be in any format or medium taking the form of writings, notes, numbers, symbols, text, images, films, video, sound recordings, pictorial reproductions, drawings, designs or other graphical representations, procedural manuals, forms, diagrams, work flow charts, equipment descriptions, data files, data processing algorithms, or statistical records. (<https://codata.org/initiatives/data-science-and-stewardship/rdm-terminology-wg/rdm-terminology/>)

Metadata

Metadata are data that describe data. Metadata can (and should) be generous and extensive, including descriptive information about the context, quality and condition, or characteristics of the data. (<https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/f2-data-described-rich-metadata/>)

Responsibilities under the PARC FAIR Data Policy

Each Researcher/Participant (entities participating in the action as beneficiaries, affiliated entities, associated partners, third parties giving in-kind contributions, subcontractors or recipients of financial support to third parties) of PARC will be required to comply with PARC FAIR Data Policy, as well as to the overarching DMP, project specific DMPs and the PARC ethics and data protection framework.

Adherence and implementation (see below, next topic) of the PFDP is a combined effort. Each Researcher/Participant has the responsibility to bring to the attention of the WP7 leadership team in a timely manner any issue that may impede adherence to the PFDP (from the PARC Description of Action (Part B)).

As presented in PARC D7.1 (the initial overarching PARC DMP), the scale of PARC requires that smaller PARC projects (each with a Project Manager) are the mechanism via which research is performed, and each PARC project is obligated to develop a project-level DMP that is consistent with the overarching DMP (in its most recent form, which is currently the initial DMP). The relationship between the project-level DMPs, the overarching PARC DMP and the PFDP (this document) is shown schematically in Figure 1 (reproduced from D7.1 the PARC Initial DMP).

Figure 1: Illustration of the relationship between the current document (the PARC FAIR Data Policy) and the PARC overarching DMP (“PARC Initial, intermediate and Final DMP deliverable”), as the two-way flow of information to and from the project-level DMPs which address the specific data needs within the particular project, but which must be fully aligned with the overarching PARC DMP and the PARC FAIR Data Policy. FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs) are a methodology, developed by GO FAIR (<https://www.go-fair.org/how-to-go-fair/fair-implementation-profile/>), through which a research community expresses its practices and decisions around FAIR. The approach involves a series of questions on how the community makes data and metadata FAIR and what ‘FAIR Enabling Resources’ (FERs) are used. A FER can hence be a tool, software, technology, standard, etc.. “Domain” refers to the different scientific domains PARC is concerned with (exposure sciences, toxicology, risk assessment etc.)

The Project Managers and their Data Champions help to safeguard the FAIRification of data, by following up the interactions between Data champions and the WP7 Data liaisons, and perform a final check on the FAIRness and Open access compliance of all project-level data / research outputs in accordance with what was described in the project-level DMP, once the project is completed. PARC R&I WP and Task leaders (i.e., of WP4, WP5, WP6 and WP8) and the PARC Management Board should create awareness of the importance of FAIRification, and must act proactively to support the implementation of the PFDP. Further, they should also

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help to resolve conflicts (e.g., at project level) that may impede the FAIRification of the project's research outputs and data. Short definitions of the roles as used within WP7, the PFDP and the DMP can be found within the section on the definition of terms.

Policy implementation

PARC Researchers/Participants are responsible for ensuring that the PFDP principles and conditions governing the handling of data are included in the project level DMP. The project level DMP must be aligned with the overarching PARC DMP (deliverable D7.1).

The details of the relation between the project level DMP and the overarching DMP are outlined in section "Preamble to PARC Initial Data Management Plan" within the overarching PARC DMP, that is Deliverable D7.1 PARC Data Management Plan V1.0.

PARC Participants are responsible for compiling a project level DMP for every research project they are coordinating and ensuring that additional PARC Participants within the project do comply to the DMP. Participants are responsible for choosing the appropriate type of licensing for their research outputs, while ensuring alignment with Creative Commons licenses (or comparable), as defined in the Grant Agreement under the OpenAIRE guidance (<https://www.openaire.eu/how-do-i-license-my-research-data>).

In order to facilitate the FAIRification of PARC data, the specific supporting activities, roles and responsibilities are defined in more detail in the overarching PARC DMP (WP 7 deliverable D7.1) and in the chapter Definitions of terms in this document (Table 1).

The task of monitoring the FAIRification process is assigned to the FAIR Implementation Taskgroup (FIT) within WP7.2, which in practice includes the provision of training and support for the process of FAIRification of datasets and support for the development of project-level DMPs.

Policy review

The PFDP is a dynamic document, as insights are gained from the PARC projects and related initiatives such as the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and other large-scale initiatives (e.g., the Research Data Alliance, CODATA, Elixir etc). It is the intention to review and to update the policy after its inception in M18.

Towards this, this first version of the PFDP (V1.1. approved by the MB/GSB and effective at 01-07-2023, with V2 delivery data M18), will remain available as a separate editable version on the PARC ANSES SharePoint, for collection of any suggestions for improvement from the PARC community.

We foresee additional formal versions being released every 2 years (October 2025, and 2027).

4. Applicable laws and regulations

Data sets and other research outputs are produced, made findable, shared and reused in compliance with legal constraints in the order of applicability of: laws, contracts, funder requirements, policies, guidelines (combined/aligned with the EU Common Open Data Platform, ECHA, Horizon Europe, OECD, Science Europe). Specifically, for the PFDP, the regulations and funder requirements, and referral to laws provided within the Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement are binding. While aiming for FAIRness and the principle of 'Open by default', it is the responsibility of Researchers/Participants to ensure decisions on this are always in compliance with applicable laws and regulations.

5. Data governance

PARC adopts the following definition for data governance, "The exercise of authority, control and shared decision making (planning, monitoring and enforcement) over the management of data assets. It refers to the overall management of the availability, usability, integrity, and security of the data employed in an enterprise" (<https://codata.org/rdm-terminology/data-governance/>),

PARC Researchers/Participants must adhere to this PFDP, as well as the overarching PARC DMP, and data governance is essential to do this. The following topics are relevant to consider in greater detail, in the context of research data governance.

Roles and responsibilities

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The roles and responsibilities of the Data Champion, Data Liaison, FAIR Implementation Taskgroup (FIT), which are developed as part of the WP7 activities, are described in table 1 under section 15. In addition, table 1 also contains descriptions of the roles and responsibilities of the Project Leaders, the institutional Data Stewards, Domain Experts (or scientist) and Data Depositors (those who upload data to repositories) and Project Leaders. The roles and responsibilities and their interactions are more extensively described in the overarching PARC DMP (deliverable D7.1).

Ownership

The Grant Agreement states that “Results are owned by the beneficiaries that generate them.” The PARC Consortium Agreement specifies: “Each Participant may transfer ownership of its own Results, including its share in jointly owned Results, provided this does not affect compliance with their obligations under the Consortium Agreement.”

Researchers/Participants should always be aware of data ownership and act correspondingly, respecting data owners right during creation of the data, data processing, FAIRification, further sharing and, accordingly, attach the appropriate license with attribution obligation to the published data.

Data valuation

Data valuation is the assessment of the economic value of data (ECHA). Data valuation is mentioned by ECHA (and is therefore included here). Within the Substance Information Exchange Fora (SIEF), ECHA aims to “facilitate the exchange of information on available data between co-registrants” (companies) for a particular chemical, for which in case valuable data are brought in, it is logical that mutual financial compensation is agreed upon. In case non-public data (e.g. from a contractor, third party, or private owner) were to be brought in into PARC, Researchers/Participants should consider and if deemed necessary and in concordance with the Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement, decide upon and execute steps for data valuation. For this, the suggested approach by ECHA serves as starting point. (page 76, Chapter 5.3: https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/23047722/peg_draft_guidance_on_data_sharing_ver40_en.pdf/e2f9ae22-1464-a3c8-4257-cacf620e4735)

Stakeholder needs

Stakeholder needs can be supported through FAIRification of (meta)data, the choice and use of (a) specific data sharing platform(s) and/or submission of data into data repositories. Note that these stakeholder needs can stem from, for example: quality, effectiveness, market, innovation (research) or regulatory objectives. The Researchers/Participants should be aware of the fact that stakeholder have needs (e.g. re-use for scientific purposes, re-use for protocol development and QC, re-use in development of chemical risk assessment strategies or policy making) whenever submitting data and act with integrity and as best as possible to enable the uptake and use of the data for various stakeholder purposes.

Warranty and liability

Within PARC the Consortium Agreement and Grant Agreement apply. When uploading research outputs to repositories outside the PARC community, Researchers/Participants should be aware that when data are made available, Researchers/Participants shall, except if agreed otherwise, to all possible extent, ensure that the following aspects are paid attention to (adapted/taken from JRC): The data are provided “as is” without warranty of any kind, either explicitly or implied. There is no obligation to provide technical support or remedies for the data. Although aim is to strive for scientifically sound data (see below under “data quality”), the Researchers/Participants do not represent or warrant that the data will be fully error free or that all non-conformities can or will be corrected, or that any data are accurate or complete, or that they are of a satisfactory technical or scientific quality. The Researchers/Participants shall not be held liable for any direct or indirect, incidental, consequential or other damages, including but not limited to the loss of data, loss of profits, or any other financial loss arising from the use of the data, or inability to use them. These aspects are applicable for Researchers/Participants submitting data to platforms, repositories, research infrastructures etc.

Process for requesting an exemption to Open Data

In case Researchers/Participants consider exemption or embargo to FAIRification and/or providing open access to the data, a full justification of the grounds for an exemption or embargo period needs to be included

in the project-level DMP. The data champion, data liaison and FAIR implementation team will discuss the issue and determine whether it is reasonable, necessary (e.g., to comply with local legal requirements) and justified, and make a recommendation to the WP7 leadership and the Data and Ethics Board for approval of the request to deviate from the PFDP. In all cases, the metadata associated with the Closed or Embargoed data will be FAIR and open, with information on who to contact to discuss access for specific purposes.

6. Data management

The PARC Grant Agreement defines research data management as: “The process within the research lifecycle that includes the organisation, storage, preservation, security, quality assurance, allocation of persistent identifiers (PIDs) and rules and procedures for sharing of data including licensing.”

Whenever possible and applicable, Researchers/Participants will make use of or build further on existing sustainable data management solutions, that can contribute to FAIR, i.e., those offered or adopted by the EC, Member States, the EOSC, and/or EC or Member State supported research infrastructures or research consortia (from the Consortium Agreement).

Data integrity

Data integrity entails that research data are accurate, original (in the format it was generated), complete, consistent, legible and in context. Data integrity also involves the implementation of measures to control the physical environment (including protection against environmental hazards) of networked terminals and servers, restricting access to data, and maintaining rigorous authentication practices.

At the research performing institutions, processes, rules, quality procedures and standards to ensure data integrity must be in place.

PARC promotes the creation, collection, sharing, handling and further dissemination of data for which the integrity can be ascertained. Therefore, in agreeing to share data, Researchers/Participants need to have assurance that their data are properly handled, disseminated and acknowledged, following similar principles and rules across countries and stakeholders (aligned with EEA).

Data curation

Curation of data entails (at a minimum) cleansing, documenting, versioning and formatting of data, addition of metadata to data, to facilitate understanding of the data and its relationships. Curation also involves the identification of anomalies and differences on properties as well as interpretation and the provision of recommendations of actions or changes to solve such differences or issues (aligned with CODATA and COPCSD (now: EU Common Data Platform on Chemicals (EU-CDPC))). Higher levels of curation involve maintaining links with annotation and with other published materials. (<https://codata.org/rdm-terminology/data-curation/>).

At the research performing institutions, a process for data curation, including explanatory documentation (e.g. SOPs), should be in place or may be implemented.

The PARC community should be aware of and committed to the importance of data curation, and act within its research and data management activities to ensure the proper curation of data.

Data quality

For data quality, we adopt the CODATA definition: “The reliability and application efficiency of data. It is a perception or an assessment of dataset’s fitness to serve its purpose in a given context. Aspects of data quality include: Accuracy, Completeness, Update status, Relevance, Consistency across data sources, Reliability, Appropriate presentation, Accessibility (<https://codata.org/rdm-terminology/data-quality/>) “

Data quality is the responsibility of the Researchers/Participants within the research projects and within the research work packages. The Grant Agreements states that to improve data quality and comparability, advanced data analysis tools and interlinked databases and algorithms to harness, combine and provide evidence and expertise on chemicals of emerging concern will be shared between WPs through training and co-implementation of case studies. In case PARC projects/work packages agree upon the use of such tools,

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databases and algorithms as well as data quality criteria/systems (e.g. ISO17025, GLP etc.), this PFDP advises PARC Researchers/Participants to follow these. If applicable, research should be performed under a quality system in order to facilitate the acceptance of research data (aligned with OECD). The DMP describes how data quality is ensured (Annotated Grant Agreement).

Within the PARC research projects, a process to control the quality of data (e.g., consistency in limit of quantification, limit of detection) should be in place and must be described in the project level DMP. Data quality assessment procedures and outcomes should be added to the metadata. Any critical issues/flaws in the data should be mentioned in the metadata, explaining the data, in order to create awareness for subsequent experts willing to use the data. It is recommended that consideration of data quality is introduced as early as possible within the data management cycle, e.g., during the design phase of the study. It needs to be emphasized that FAIR as such does not increase and is not equal to high data quality.

DMP

All PARC Projects should create and update if appropriate at the end of the project a DMP, in line with this PFDP as well as the overarching DMP and if exceptions are made these should be justified.

PARC defines the DMP as defined in the PARC Consortium Agreement as follows: “A document that outlines from the start of the project the main aspects of the (data management) lifecycle of research outputs, notably including data. This includes their provenance, organisation and curation, as well as adequate provisions for their access, preservation, sharing, and eventual deletion, both during and after PARC.”

Establishing and adhering to a DMP can help to improve research quality and FAIRification. Examples of how researchers can benefit from using an timely implemented DMP are: to reconsider or refine the experimental design; to avoid loss and/or time consuming tracing of data once the research is finished; to assist/facilitate in the scientific reporting.

PARC Researchers/Participants should use a software tool to capture and store the (project specific) DMP (a preferred software tool will be proposed later by WP7), with inclusion of the following reference to the PARC project: “Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals, <https://doi.org/10.3030/101057014>” . PARC Researchers/Participants should embrace training opportunities in the use of these tools, provided by WP7.

Further details on the compliance of the PARC consortium with the overarching DMP are defined in Paragraph 8.5 of the Consortium Agreement.

Documentation

Documentation on data, in any form (DMPs, scientific publications, reports, FIP), should be made available in order for researchers to understand (and reproduce) the data (aligned with EOSC, Horizon Europe, IPCHEM). It is expected that all datasets created with PARC funding, are made available either preceding or with accompanying documentation or DMPs, scientific publications, reports, together with the actual submission of the data to PARC specific project databases and repositories. The metadata include references to the accompanying documentation or DMPs, scientific publications, reports as well as vice versa.

Research integrity

Traceability, openness, provenance, submission etc. of data, in fact all relevant aspects in relation to FAIR and open data, may be potentially compromised in case Researchers/Participants do not act with integrity. Therefore, this PFDP reemphasizes the statements on being compliant with ethics and integrity as contained in the Grant Agreement/Consortium Agreement: “The beneficiaries must pay particular attention to the principle of proportionality, the right to privacy, the right to the protection of personal data, the right to the physical and mental integrity of persons, the right to non-discrimination, the need to ensure protection of the environment and high levels of human health protection.” PARC Researchers/Participants are expected to comply with The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (<https://www.allera.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/05/ALLEA-European-Code-of-Conduct-for-Research-Integrity-2017.pdf>), which says the following: “Good research practices are based on fundamental principles of research integrity. They guide Participants in their work as well as in their engagement with the practical, ethical and intellectual challenges inherent in research”. It is foreseen that additional information on research integrity specifically applicable for PARC comes available through the PARC Ethics and Data Protection Board deliverables.

In addition, where PARC Researchers/Participants use data in AI/ML, they are expected to comply with the EC Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI (<https://ec.europa.eu/futurium/en/ai-alliance-consultation.1.html>), which contains key requirements including privacy, data security, data integrity, data quality, data access and transparency.

7. Data security

Researchers/Participants must verify, at their institution, that during the research their data are stored and can be transferred/exchanged securely. The data, along with relevant meta-data and descriptions, should be protected against intentional or unintentional loss, destruction, modification and unauthorized access in conformity with explicit security protocols. Data sets and the equipment on which they are stored should also be protected from environmental hazards (see also OECD). The project level DMP specifies which provisions are in place to ensure data security.

8. Repositories

In line with the PARC Grant Agreement Researchers/Participants should manage the research data generated within projects responsibly, by ensuring, within the deadlines described in the DMP, the deposition of the data into a trusted repository, which must be federated in the EOSC and in compliance with EOSC requirements (see <https://eosc-portal.eu/>).

The project specific DMPs must specify which repository will be used. Specialised, acknowledged and trusted, FAIR-enabling repositories should be prioritized for data submission. As a general rule, PARC funded data should be in a domain specific EU repository. Preference should be given to repositories which guarantee long retention times (like e.g., Zenodo). Retention times should comply with legal and institutional requirements (see for example the data policy from Utrecht University). The EU Annotated Model Grant Agreement clarifies in detail the requirements for trusted repositories (starting on page 283, the direct link to the relevant page is https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/guidance/aga_en.pdf#page=283). In short, trusted repositories are certified or endorsed repositories, repositories which display specific characteristics of organisational, technical and procedural quality, provide broad, equitable and ideally open access, facilitate mid- and long-term preservation of the deposited material.

It is however acknowledged that the trustworthiness and as well the FAIRness of repositories may be difficult to assess. Careful consideration should also be made toward the avoidance of vendor lock in, whether intentional or not. For example, data egress fees from commercial vendors can sometimes be prohibitive effectively preventing data from ever being moved to other platforms. Data egress fees are charged by cloud providers for data transfer from the cloud storage where the data was uploaded.

Therefore, Researchers/Participants must seek advice from experienced data experts who can evaluate the sustainability, trustworthiness, and risk of vendor lock-in on repository services. Also, existing repositories which may have only a core set of metadata, may be augmented with resources such as rich metadata repositories. A metadata repository is an accessible database containing metadata, but not the data.

Resource accreditation

Researchers/Participants should be aware that for providers of data and data services, external accreditation is increasingly desirable, and sometimes essential, in building the necessary trust with important user communities, partner service providers, or both. Examples of external accreditation are CoreTrustSeal, ISO27001, FitSM, ISO16363 or see the [GO-FAIR initiative on certification](#).

Sustainability

Long-term sustainability of data and services is a requirement for trusted repositories (EU Annotated Model Grant Agreement). Participants must ensure that repositories have a long-term preservation policy or roadmap in place, describing for example storage, backup, transfer of formats and documentation (EU FAIRSFAR recommendation).

9. Transparency and openness

PARC (see Grant Agreement, Consortium Agreement) embraces transparency and openness concerning data generated in PARC, whenever possible, as this will foster innovative risk assessment.

Transparency

The OECD defines transparency as “Information on research data and data-producing organisations, documentation on the data and specifications of conditions attached to the use of these data should be internationally available in a transparent way, ideally through the Internet. Lack of visibility of existing research data resources and future data collection poses serious obstacles to access.”.

Openness

The OECD defines openness as “access on equal terms for the international research community at the lowest possible cost, preferably at no more than the marginal cost of dissemination.”.

Open science

Open science is about knowledge as well as data (EU).

“Challenges for risk assessment and risk management can only be addressed in an open and collaborative way. Therefore, the implementation of Open Science practices in PARC is strategic. In the context of Open Science, PARC will promote the organization of data and the exchange between different actors (scientific community, health agencies, regulators, policy-makers etc.) and disciplines (e.g. exposure science, toxicology) to promote transparency, support risk assessment, and allow for re-use” (from the PARC Project Description of Action (Part B)).

Open data

Open data are data in an open format that can be freely used, re-used and shared by anyone for any purpose (EOSC). 'Timely and comprehensive' are critical components of Open Data.

With timely, it is meant that the individual PARC Participant/Researcher/Project Leader can consider the most appropriate moment in time to make the (non-meta) data open. This can be before or simultaneously with the publication of a paper or report. Alternatively the data cannot be disclosed given that the PARC Grant Agreement states ‘as open as possible, **as closed as necessary**’, effectively “open by default, **unless...**”.

Closely related to open data is open access: “Possibility to access and re-use digital research outputs with as few restrictions as possible (EOSC)”

The Grant Agreement states that “FAIR and open data sharing according to the ‘as open as possible, as closed as necessary’ principle will be the default for PARC and applied to all research outputs (including reports, data, software, guidelines, method descriptions, formats, templates, semantic artefacts (ontologies, vocabularies etc.)). The default option will be that all research outputs will be made openly available, unless this has to be restricted due to legal reasons, consent, privacy, confidentiality or Intellectual Property Rights (IPR). Thus: unless providing open access would in particular be against the Participant’s legitimate interests, including regarding commercial exploitation, or be contrary to any other constraints, in particular the EU competitive interests or the Participants’ obligations under the PARC Consortium Agreement.”

Embargo

Data sets may be deposited under restricted or open access. Access to data can be embargoed by submitters and submitters provide the end date for the embargo (based on EU Annotated Model Grant Agreement, see for example Zenodo). The Annotated Grant Agreement states to deposit the generated research data “as soon as possible and within the deadlines set out in the DMP, to ensure open access ---” and “, unless providing open access would in particular: be against the beneficiary’s legitimate interests, including regarding commercial exploitation, or be contrary to any other constraints, in particular the EU competitive interests or the beneficiary’s obligations under this Agreement; if open access is not provided (to some or all data), this must be justified in the DMP”.

Data Availability Statement.

PARC Researchers/Participants will provide a Data Availability Statement, with their publications/reporting, to indicate the research data associated with a scientific publication is available, and under what conditions the data can be accessed. (EU FAIRSFair recommendation). Note that providing data as supplementary materials to (peer reviewed) publications does not replace the requirement to deposit the data in a trusted certified repository.

10. FAIR

The Consortium Agreement states that “Subject to confidentiality obligations and applicable data protection rules, every Participant must manage the digital research data it generates (Data) or uses in PARC responsibly, in line with the FAIR principles ('Findable', 'Accessible', 'Interoperable' and 'Reusable')." Note, that the A in FAIR, in more detail, stands for 'Accessible under well-defined conditions' and does not imply either open or closed. In addition to the FAIR Principles and Access control, the GO FAIR Foundation has recommended three other criteria for consideration for the publication of FAIR data: decentralization as a default, an overall hourglass architecture placing minimal open standards between applications and infrastructure services and the avoidance of vendor lock in whether it is intentional or accidental (<https://www.gofair.foundation/criteria>).

As stated in the PARC Grant Agreement: “Data will be made FAIR at the source whenever possible, described by FAIR metadata, and associated with a persistent identifier. This means that the inclusion of a persistent identifier is mandatory for all metadata within PARC, enabling connection to underlying data if open access can be granted.

(see further below under “persistent identifiers”)

“Metadata should be in line with the FAIR principles, in particular, it [*Responsible author(s): metadata*] should be machine-actionable (which means machine readable, and automatic computer processing can extract information from the metadata attributes ensuring a cross-linking between different research outputs) and follow a standardised format, in line with community standards, and should provide rich information” (EU Annotated Model Grant Agreement).

The DMP describes the FAIR implementation choices when applicable. The research data may be closed if necessary, but the metadata must be open (in line with OpenAIRE).

FAIRification is the practical stepwise process by which data are transformed into formats that follow open standards for interoperability. This transformation makes the data FAIR-ready and opens the door to machine-processing (GO-FAIR).

Data FAIRification will be a key activity of PARC to facilitate data reuse. Data will be made FAIR at the source whenever possible, described by FAIR metadata, and associated with a persistent identifier. WP7 will set up specific methods and tools and guidance to FAIRify data and facilitate data reuse in the Research & Innovation WPs and in regulatory agencies (Grant Agreement). Recommendations or guidance following the WP7 task on this may be included in a next version of the PFDP, including details of the FAIR Enabling Resources identified as being suitable for use in PARC, as captured in the PARC FAIR Implementation Profile(s). (For the explanation of the terms FAIR Enabling Resources (FERs) and FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs) see the caption of Figure 1.)

Section 10.5 will in more detail describe the FAIR ambition of PARC.

Below additional information is given for the FAIR principles in the context of PARC.

10.1. Findable

Metadata can (and should) be generous and extensive, including descriptive information about the context, quality and condition, or characteristics of the data. Machine-readable metadata are essential for automatic discovery of datasets and services, so this is an essential component of the FAIRification process (GO-FAIR).

The research data may be closed if necessary, but the metadata must be FAIR (in line with OpenAIRE).

(Meta)data schemas

A standard metadata model (or metadata schema) should be used to ease discovery of research data and metadata (rephrased/aligned with EOSC, EU Annotated Model Grant Agreement).

Persistent Identifiers

The EU Annotated Model Grant Agreement (page 159) states that: “Importantly, Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) must be provided for the dataset (such as a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) or a handle), for all author(s) involved in the action (such as ORCIDs or ResearcherIDs) and, if possible, for their organizations (such as ROR IDs) and the grant (such as grant DOIs).” The term 'handle' in the above citation refers to the Handle system (<http://www.handle.net/>) used by DOI system (<https://www.doi.org/>). The application of globally unique, persistent and resolvable identifiers continues to evolve and we expect further innovations in the coming years that may impact the PFDP and DMP.

10.2. Accessible

Once the user finds the required data, the user needs to know how they can be accessed, possibly including authentication and authorization (GO-FAIR). One of the central goals of promoting data access and sharing is to improve the overall efficiency of publicly funded scientific research to avoid the expensive and unnecessary duplication of data collection efforts (OECD).

It is promoted to provide easy (i.e., automated) access to data sources, available in different formats (aligned with EOSC). If needed, multiple levels of access should be considered (see for example IPCHEM). Although data and metadata will likely be increasingly decentralized, it is preferred to have a single or only a few access point(s) to the data (see for example JRC, EU Common Data Platform on Chemicals (EU-CDPC) or the NORMAN Database System (NDS)).

It may make sense to request users to create a user account for a repository, which implicates the choice of the repository (see for example JRC). A user account allows to authenticate the owner (or contributor) of each dataset, to set user-specific rights. It is anticipated under “data visiting” scenarios that authorization and authentication will be extended to certified algorithms where access control will involve automated agents. Emerging examples of best practice include the Swiss Health Network and the German Swarm Learning initiatives (<https://www.nature.com/articles/s41586-021-03583-3>). Note that metadata should persist even when the data are no longer retained (GO FAIR).

10.3. Interoperable

The data usually need to be integrated with other data. In addition, the data need to interoperate with applications or workflows for analysis, storage, and processing (GO-FAIR).

The PARC Grant Agreement states that: “The aim of the Partnership is to enable all the scientific communities involved in chemical RA, as well as risk managers and stakeholders, to have access to high-quality data by facilitating their accessibility, interoperability and usefulness for research.” The DMPs will describe specific choices for standards to ensure interoperability.

The concept of interoperability can be structured according to four layers: technical, semantic, organizational and legal (EOSC), which should be taken into consideration.

Technical interoperability.

Technical interoperability can be defined as the ability of different information technology systems and software applications to communicate with one another, enabling the exchange of data as well as metadata (based on EOSC). This layer includes open specifications, open protocols and easy access to data sources available in different formats specifications (based on EOSC).

Semantic interoperability.

Semantic interoperability can be defined as “the ability of computer systems to transmit data with unambiguous, shared meaning”. This layer is mainly dealing with publicly available definitions for the concepts, documentation, minimal set of common metadata formats and shared semantic artefacts (ontologies, thesauri) (EOSC).

Organisational interoperability

Organisational interoperability refers to the way in which organisations align their business processes, responsibilities and expectations to achieve commonly agreed and mutually beneficial goals (EOSC).

Legal interoperability

Legal interoperability requires, in particular, that data should be reusable. It concerns the ability to combine datasets from multiple sources without conflicts among restrictions imposed by the license of each dataset (EOSC).

10.4. Reusable

The ultimate goal of FAIR is to optimize the reuse of data. To achieve this, metadata and data should be well-described so that they can be replicated and/or combined in different settings (GO-FAIR).

PARC Participants support the wider exploitation, re-use and re-combination of data from different sources in different frameworks and media than those for which they were originally commissioned (aligned with EEA). This implies that all PARC Participants should be aware that the data they create to address their primary scientific hypothesis or data gap filling needs, should always be possibly reusable (if allowed) as to accommodate new research/and or risk assessment purposes.

In line with Horizon Europe, PARC asks from Participants to provide detailed information about research outputs or tools/instruments needed to re-use or validate the data (e.g., DMPs, data, software, algorithms, protocols, models, workflows, electronic notebooks, publications).

Provenance

Provenance (or lineage) is the documentation of why and how the data (and other research output) was produced, where, when and by whom. Data provenance/lineage means tracing the movements and the changes of the data that occurred between their origin and their destination system (aligned with EEA, EOSC, definition based on ELIXIR).

For PARC projects, the DMP describes the data provenance to be able to assess data integrity and authenticity.

Licenses

The Annotated Grant Agreement requires that “Research data made open access must be licensed under the latest version of a Creative Commons Attribution International Public License (CC BY) requiring attribution of authorship, or a license providing equivalent rights, or under a Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC0) or equivalent (which waives any rights to the data). The latter may be appropriate in particular for large datasets that can be more easily reused without restrictions, or in any other case if authors so desire. A Creative Commons Public Domain Mark (PDM) or equivalent should be applied to raw research data unless the data meet the requirements to be protected by copyright/database right.”

Regarding metadata, the Annotated Grant Agreement requires “Additionally, metadata must be open access under a CC0 public domain dedication or equivalent, to the extent legitimate interests are safeguarded and constraints are considered. In cases where data is closed but there are no compelling reasons that the related metadata should not be findable and accessible, it is recommended that open access be provided to the metadata of the data, with CC0 public domain dedication or equivalent, if possible, while the dataset itself remains closed.”

In line with the FAIR principles all published data sets need an appropriate and machine-readable license.

10.5. PARC's Ambition in relation to FAIR data

A key topic being discussed currently, and discussed at the Teams consultation meetings on the PARC FAIR data policy, is how far to go in terms of FAIR. The PARC FAIR roadmap (which is part of the second annual work plan) will elaborate further on this. Data can be increasingly FAIR, as shown schematically in Figure 2. The ambition for PARC is to strive towards FAIR, Open and linked data (Panel F in Figure 2) but recognizing that (a) resources are limited, (b) not every sub-domain within PARC is equally far along the road to FAIRness, and (c) not all Participants / Researchers are as experienced in FAIR, and (d) technical constraints may have to be solved. **PARC will strive for a minimum level of FAIRness for all PARC data and metadata, whether it is Open or Closed, as shown in Panels D and E in Figure 2 below.** In some cases, Panel C may apply for data that would require big efforts to FAIRify them as compared to the potential benefits.

Data as increasingly FAIR Digital Objects

Figure 2. Varying degrees of FAIRness (A unfair, to F fully FAIR and Linked). As elements become coloured, they have become FAIR. For example, adding a persistent identifier (PID) increases the fairness of that component (B). Elements coloured in green are FAIR and open (E), elements coloured in red are FAIR and closed (D). In the final panel (F), the mechanism for expressing the relationship between the ID, the metadata, and the data, is also FAIR (i.e., it follows a widely accepted and machine-readable standard, such as DCAT or NanoPublications) and interlinked with other related FAIR data or analytical tools on the Internet of FAIR Data and Services. Figure taken from Mons et al., 2017, 10.3233/ISU-170824.

The aspects that ultimately influence the FAIR ambitions, currently considered (from a time, resource and current tooling and capability perspective), and which will become part of the PARC FAIR roadmap are as follows: the level of FAIRness ambition may raise with the years in PARC; the PARC Researchers/Participants will become more aware and gain expertise, tools and training on FAIR, which may help to achieve a higher level of ambition.

Per project the level of ultimate FAIRness is influenced by the amount of metadata versus raw data versus processed data; raw data versus processed versus summarized; regulatory versus research requirements.

11. Intellectual property

The PARC Grant Agreement defines access rights as: “Rights to use results or background.” The terms “results” and “background” are further defined in the Consortium Agreement. The Grant Agreement describes in detail (access rights to) background and results, ownership of results, rights of use, intellectual property rights (IPR) under Article 16 plus additional information. Although the aim is to foster FAIRification, Researchers/Participants should always be in compliance with these terms.

Intellectual property

As stated in the PARC Grant Agreement: “Beneficiaries (or authors) must retain sufficient intellectual property rights to comply with the open access requirements.”

Data citation

Participants are expected to properly cite data sets as is also practice for publications (EU FAIRSFAR recommendation).

12. Sensitive data

Personal data

Personal data must be obtained and used in compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (Regulation EU 2016/679, GDPR) and with the informed consent that has been given by the data subject.

Researchers/Participants that collect, process or use personal data, have to take all necessary measures to adhere to the GDPR, national data protection regulations and other ethical regulations as described in the Grant Agreement.

Personal data are collected and used only when an informed consent by the subject is given, covering the use of the data to reach PARC objectives. Informed consents will be drafted in such a way that they allow maximum possibilities for future reuse of the data, even beyond PARC, including use for regulatory purposes. The GDPR clearly explains the obligations to be met (<https://gdpr.eu/gdpr-consent-requirements/>). GDPR proof consent forms were developed by HBM4EU and are available on Zenodo (doi:10.5281/zenodo.6513996; doi:10.5281/zenodo.6517154). PARC is further adapting these consent forms, i.e., to make reuse of personal data by EU administrations and agencies possible. For studies that are initiated during PARC and that use PARC resources for generating data, the data subject shall consent that the data is collected within the context of the EU partnership PARC and that the data can be reused for research and policy making at EU level. A standard statement to be included in the informed consent, will be made available for that purpose.¹

Use of data should adhere to the GDPR principle of data minimalization, i.e. Researchers/Participants involved in the processing of the data, shall only get access to the specific variables and records of the dataset that are necessary to answer PARC research questions (or to answer specified questions related to reuse beyond PARC).

In line with GDPR data controller and data processor agreements have to be concluded between data providing Researchers/Participants and data using Researchers/Participants. These can be bilateral as well as multilateral. The *Protocol on the management and use of Personal Exposure and Health Data Platform* (https://hbm.vito.be/sites/hbm4eu/files/inline-files/PEH%20Data%20Platform%20-%20Protocol_informative%20website.pdf) based on experience drawn from the HBM4EU project, provides a good example of a flexible multilateral governance system and agreement for multilateral exchange of data extracted from multiple datasets.

Although experience has been gained in several European or national research projects and initiatives in the health domain and more specifically in the environment and health domain (Govarts, et al, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.envint.2022.107334), and PARC will build further for providing specific recommendations, researchers/Participants should always consult their DPO before sharing or using personal data, or concluding agreements.

The evolution of the PFDP on sensitive data and its related FAIRification efforts will include lessons learnt (from pilots in PARC as well as from national health data initiatives) on federated analysis techniques (“data visiting”)

¹ This statement could be similar to: “I consent that my coded samples and/or data can be transferred to specialized laboratories, biobanks, databases, data infrastructures, research establishments, administrative authorities and institutions in the European Union and associated countries and that samples and/or data are used within the scope of the research.”

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in which algorithms are executed on federated data sets without the need to share the data with the data analyst that provides the algorithm.

Commercial data

Researchers/Participants must be aware and act accordingly when (meta)data are potential commercially valuable, such as patent filing or trade secrets, and these (meta)data must not be disclosed.

13. Archiving

Preservation

It is required that Researchers/Participants consider the long-term preservation of data and related information (data package), beyond the lifespan of the PARC project, while avoiding where possible potential vendor lockin, at the outset of each new project, and in particular, determine the most appropriate institutional archival facilities for the data before the data are submitted to public accessible repositories (Annotated Grant Agreement, aligned with OECD). The DMP describes the provisions for long-term preservation of data (Annotated Grant Agreement).

Retention and deletion

OpenAIRE states that basic research data and related material should be retained for a minimum of 10 years after the study has been completed. This approach can be considered as a basic best practice. However, Researchers/Participants must comply with legally required retention times for types of research data (e.g., drug research, medical research, personal data) and for other special reasons which are directed by law, local or institutional policies and other agreements (see for example Utrecht University).

Additionally, Researchers/Participants should consider potential future scientific/regulatory reasons and needs that would justify the retention of data beyond this 10 year best practice. Reasons could be : e.g. long term time trend analysis in human data; reanalysis of data with novel data analysis methods, meta analyses etc.

Retention times as well as the eventual deletion, both during and after PARC (Grant Agreement) is written in the DMP. For data that are to be destroyed, a secure and protocolised manner must be followed under the responsibility of the appropriate manager at the research performing organisation, but metadata about the dataset MUST remain available and open. This implies some measure of discretionary control by PARC data stewards (Data Liaisons and Data Champions) over data storage, transfer and deletion operations which could be impacted by the choice of repository.

14. References

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This initiative is now termed: EU Common Data Platform on Chemicals (EU-CDPC))

ECHA; Access to documents; Access to documents

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https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/17208/mb_61_2014_echa_transparency_en.pdf/068580f5-a523-4fb0-9fb8-90fd27c5277a?t=1419327138730

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ECHA; Guidance on data sharing; Data sharing

ECHA; How to protect your confidential business information; Practical example for the R2018 portal (europa.eu)

ECHA; Legal Notice; .europa.eu/legal-notice

ECHA; Personal data protection. ; Personal data protection - ECHA (europa.eu)

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EFSA; Data collection; Data collection

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EOSC; A Service Provider's Guide to Data Sharing Policies; InfoCards_A4_June2020 v7.pdf (eosc-hub.eu)

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European Commission; Data governance and data policies at the European Commission; https://commission.europa.eu/publications/data-governance-and-data-policies-european-commission_en

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Horizon Europe; Horizon Europe Open Science requirements in practice; Horizon Europe Open Science requirements in practice – OpenAIRE webinar | Zenodo

IPCHEM; IPCHEM – PARTICIPATION FORM; https://ipchem.jrc.ec.europa.eu/documents/IPCHEM_ParticipationForm_V3.docx

IPCHEM; IPCHEM – The Information Platform for Chemical Monitoring: Data Policy; https://ipchem.jrc.ec.europa.eu/documents/IPCHEM_DataPolicy_V3.pdf

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OECD; OECD Principles and Guidelines for Access to Research Data from Public Funding; <http://www.oecd.org/science/sci-tech/38500813.pdf>

OpenAIRE; Horizon Europe Open Science requirements in practice; <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/d787ea54-6a87-11eb-aeb5-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

OpenAIRE; Model Open Science Policy for Research Performing Organisations; <https://www.openaire.eu/model-policy-on-open-science-for-research-performing-organisations>

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OpenAIRE; Model Policy on Open Science for Research Funding Organisations (RFOs) ; <https://www.openaire.eu/model-policy-on-open-science-for-research-funding-organisations>

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PLOS; PLOS Open Data policy; <https://journals.plos.org/plosone/s/data-availability>

Science Europe; Science Europe Guidance Document. Presenting a Framework for Discipline-specific Research Data Management; <https://www.google.com/search?q=Science+Europe+Guidance+Document&oq=Science+Europe+Guidance+Document&aqs=edge..69i57j69i60.502j0j4&sourceid=chrome&ie=UTF-8&safe=active&ssui=on>

Unesco; UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science; <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000379949.locale=en>

Utrecht University; Data policy Utrecht university; https://www.uu.nl/sites/default/files/university_policy_framework_for_research_data_utrecht_university_-_january_2016.pdf

Zenodo; Zenodo General Policies; <https://about.zenodo.org/policies/>

15. Definitions of terms

Table 1. Definitions of Roles Defined within WP7, the PFDP and the DMP

Term	Definition of roles
Data Champion	Data Champions are appointed by each PARC project to “champion” the need for proactive data management and feed issues that arise in the data management back to WP7. FAIR data champions are scientific experts and are hands-on in the field of FAIR data. The Champions work as FAIR ambassadors, sharing FAIR implementation stories, enhancing synergies, contributing to training activities and webinars, and encouraging cross-domain engagement with FAIR (see also section 1.1.1 in this document and the WP7 Role description).
Data Liaison	Data Liaisons from within WP7 have overarching data management knowledge (and receive additional training) and preferably domain-specific knowledge that are appointed to “support” the PARC projects and Data Champions in developing their DMPs. The data liaison is a key person in use case identification based on the PARC project descriptions of the WPs 4,5,6 and 8 (see also section 1.1.1 in this document and the WP7 Role description).
Data Steward	The research data steward, positioned at the research institution, supports and works in close collaboration with the main data producers and users in academia: the researchers, ranging from undergraduate students to full professors. The data steward advises researchers, makes sure data is handled in a manner compliant with the institute’s policy and may also perform hands-on work in a project (ELIXIR).
Domain Expert	A scientist or informatician with deep knowledge of a specific domain and its norms in terms of data generation, data manipulation and data management. The term domain refers to the scientific domain of activity, e.g., environmental monitoring versus human biomonitoring, toxicity / ecotoxicity, etc. If projects are clustered per scientific domain, then the term domain closely aligns with a cluster of projects.
Data depositors	All Researchers/Participants are allowed to deposit data sets in a repository, that is to act as “a data depositor”, provided they possess the appropriate rights to do so.
FAIR Implementation Taskgroup (FIT)	The tasks and responsibilities of the FIT will include all of the activities outlined above for Data Liaisons plus the following additional aspects: Receive significant training on the technical processes including FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs) and Metadata for Machines (M4M), such that they gain confidence to facilitate and support others in application of these approaches. Development of domain-specific and use-case FIPs, in collaboration with GO FAIR Foundation, WP7 colleagues and domain experts. Development of domain-specific and use-case metadata, in collaboration with GO FAIR Foundation, WP7 colleagues and domain experts. Provision of expertise to support PARC-projects in the delivery and implementation of their DMP, including where needed, recommendations for new Use cases to facilitate development of bespoke solutions to address needs / gaps.

	Lead the FIP development and implementation for new Use-cases identified from projects (WP7 Role description).
Project Leaders	Project leaders (PL) manage their respective projects and are the key contact point between TL and organisations implementing the project. In collaboration with the Task co-leaders, the Project leaders are in charge of driving the work of the involved organisations (resource requirement assessment, completion of project templates, etc.) to ensure that the projects are smoothly implemented. (from the PARC Handbook V3)

Table 2: Definition of Terms used in the PARC FAIR Data Policy

Term	Definition
Accessible	Once the user finds the required data, the user needs to know how they can be accessed, possibly including authentication and authorization (GO-FAIR). One of the central goals of promoting data access and sharing is to improve the overall efficiency of publicly funded scientific research to avoid the expensive and unnecessary duplication of data collection efforts (OECD). (FAIR Principles - GO FAIR, go-fair.org)
Aim of the policy	Outlines the aim, purpose of the PARC data policy (own definition)
Applicable laws and regulations	The legal regulations and law(s) applicable to (aspects of) the data policy, resources from which snippets were retrieved (own definition)
Citizen science	Many definitions see link. One from these: EU (2016): "Inclusion of non-institutional participants, in other words the general public, in the scientific process" (Haklay, M., Dörler, D., Heigl, F., Manzoni, M., Hecker, S., Vohland, K. (2021). What Is Citizen Science? The Challenges of Definition. In: The Science of Citizen Science. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-58278-4_2)
Confidentiality	Confidentiality. 1. The duties and practices of people and organizations to ensure that an individuals' personal information only flows from one entity to another according to legislated or otherwise broadly accepted norms and policies. 2. In the context of health data: Confidentiality is breached whenever personal information is communicated that is not authorized by legislation, professional obligations, or under contractual duties. (https://codata.org/rdm-terminology/confidentiality/)
Data	Facts, measurements, recordings, records, or observations about the world collected by scientists and others, with a minimum of contextual interpretation. Data may be in any format or medium taking the form of writings, notes, numbers, symbols, text, images, films, video, sound recordings, pictorial reproductions, drawings, designs or other graphical representations, procedural manuals, forms, diagrams, work flow charts, equipment descriptions, data files, data processing algorithms, or statistical records. (https://codata.org/rdm-terminology/data/)

Data access	The continued, available for use, ongoing usability of a digital resource, retaining all qualities of authenticity, accuracy and functionality deemed to be essential for the purposes the digital material was created and/or acquired for. Users who have access can retrieve, manipulate, copy, and store copies on a wide range of hard drives and external devices. (https://codata.org/rdm-terminology/access/)
Data Availability Statement	When submitting a manuscript, authors must provide a Data Availability Statement describing compliance with PLOS' data policy. If the article is accepted for publication, the Data Availability Statement will be published as part of the article (https://journals.plos.org/plosone/s/data-availability)
Data citation	Data citation is provided in a similar way that researchers routinely include bibliographic references to traditionally published resources. (https://codata.org/rdm-terminology/data-citation/)
Data curation	A managed process, throughout the data lifecycle, by which data/data collections are cleansed, documented, standardized, formatted and inter-related. This includes versioning data, or forming a new collection from several data sources, annotating with metadata, adding codes to raw data (e.g., classifying a galaxy image with a galaxy type such as "spiral"). Higher levels of curation involve maintaining links with annotation and with other published materials. Thus, a dataset may include a citation link to publication whose analysis was based on the data. The goal of curation is to manage and promote the use of data from its point of creation to ensure it is fit for contemporary purpose and available for discovery and re-use. For dynamic datasets this may mean continuous enrichment or updating to keep it fit for purpose. Special forms of curation may be available in data repositories. The data curation process itself must be documented as part of curation. Thus, curation and provenance are highly related. (https://codata.org/rdm-terminology/data-curation/)
Data depositor	Submission of primary data and derived information to public data repositories is an essential step in the scientific process. Through submission, the scientific community is fed the raw materials for the building and maintenance of the complete and up-to-date data sets that support searches and analysis on the latest sequences, structures and molecular profiles of living systems. Serving as a complement to the literature publication process and supporting early data sharing. (https://www.ebi.ac.uk/submission/)
Data governance	The exercise of authority, control and shared decision making (planning, monitoring and enforcement) over the management of data assets. It refers to the overall management of the availability, usability, integrity, and security of the data employed in an enterprise. (https://codata.org/rdm-terminology/data-governance/)
Data integrity	Data integrity requires that data be complete, accurate, consistent, and in context. Codata: In the context of data and network security: The assurance that information can only be accessed or modified by those authorized to do so. Measures taken to ensure integrity include controlling the physical environment of networked terminals and servers, restricting access to data, and maintaining rigorous authentication practices. Data integrity can also be threatened by environmental hazards, such as heat, dust, and electrical surges. (https://codata.org/rdm-terminology/integrity/)

Data management	The activities of data policies, data planning, data element standardization, information management control, data synchronization, data sharing, and database development, including practices and projects that acquire, control, protect, deliver and enhance the value of data and information. SYNONYM. Data coordination (https://codata.org/rdm-terminology/data-management/)
Research data management	The PARC Grant Agreement defines research data management as: "The process within the research lifecycle that includes the organisation, storage, preservation, security, quality assurance, allocation of persistent identifiers (PIDs) and rules and procedures for sharing of data including licensing."
Data management plan (DMP)	A formal statement describing how research data will be managed and documented throughout a research project and the terms regarding the subsequent deposit of the data with a data repository for long-term management and preservation. (https://codata.org/rdm-terminology/data-management-plan/)
Data protection	Remark definition from elixier, mainly confined to protection of personal data "Where scientific research involves the processing of data concerning people in the EU, it is subject to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). The GDPR applies a "special regime" to research, providing derogations from some obligations given appropriate criteria are met and safeguards are in place. The criteria is to follow standards in research method and ethics, as well as to aim societal benefit rather than serving private interests in research. The safeguards are a multitude and include: data collection with informed consent under ethical oversight and accountability, ensuring lawful processing and exchange of human-subject information, putting in place organisational and technical data protection measures such as encryption and pseudonymisation. The practical impact of the GDPR on research is, then, establishing these safeguards within projects"; (https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/data_protection)
Data quality	The reliability and application efficiency of data. It is a perception or an assessment of dataset's fitness to serve its purpose in a given context. Aspects of data quality include: Accuracy, Completeness, Update status, Relevance, Consistency across data sources, Reliability, Appropriate presentation, Accessibility (https://codata.org/rdm-terminology/data-quality/)
Data reuse	Data reuse means using data for other purposes than it was originally collected for. (https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/reusing)

Data security	"Security. Specific attention should be devoted to supporting the use of techniques and instruments to guarantee the integrity and security of research data. With regard to guaranteeing the integrity of a data set, every effort should be made to ensure the completeness of data and absence of errors. With regard to security, the data, along with relevant meta-data and descriptions, should be protected against intentional or unintentional loss, destruction, modification and unauthorised access in conformity with explicit security protocols. Data sets and the equipment on which they are stored should be protected as well from environmental hazards such as heat, dust, electrical surges, magnetism, and electrostatic discharges. " (https://www.oecd.org/sti/inno/38500813.pdf)
Data valuation	Data valuation is the assessment of the economic value of data. (https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/2324906/guidance_on_data_sharing_en.pdf/545e4463-9e67-43f0-852f-35e70a8ead60?t=1669385322122)
Definitions	Refers to for example paragraphs in the data policies, documents in which the definitions used in the document are further explained. (own definition)
Discoverability	Discoverability is the degree to which something, especially a piece of content or information, can be found in a search of a file, database, or other information system. Discoverability is a concern in library and information science, many aspects of digital media, software and web development, and in marketing, since products and services cannot be used if people cannot find it or do not understand what it can be used for. (Wikipedia)
Documentation	Data-level documentation includes information about specific data files like: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data type • Structure of the data, e.g. questions, variables, concepts • Data processing procedures, ... and so on (this list is not exhaustive); Project-level documentation Project- or study-level documentation describes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • When, how and why the data were generated and by whom • How the data were processed • What quality assurance measures have been used, ... and so on (this list is not exhaustive) (https://howtofair.dk/how-to-fair/metadata/#what-are-metadata)
Embargo	If there is some legitimate reason not to make the data Open for some period, it is possible to embargo the data (delay access for a specified time) or restrict who gets access to data. (https://data.4tu.nl/info/gebruik/faq)
FAIR	Findable, Accesible, Interoperable, Reusable. The first step in (re)using data is to find them. Metadata and data should be easy to find for both humans and computers. Machine-readable metadata are essential for automatic discovery of datasets and services, so this is an essential component of the FAIRification process. Once the user finds the required data, she/he/they need to know how they can be accessed, possibly including authentication and authorisation. The ultimate goal of FAIR is to optimise the reuse of data. To achieve this, metadata and data should be well-described so that they can be replicated and/or combined in different settings. (https://www.gofair.foundation/interpretation)

FAIRification	FAIRification is the process by which data are transformed into formats that follow open standards for interoperability. For example, measurements captured as “free-text” in an Excel spreadsheet can be FAIRified by reformatting them into RDF triples, following a community endorsed schema and using controlled vocabularies. This transformation makes the data FAIR-ready and opens the door to machine-processing. (https://content.iospress.com/articles/fair-connect/fc221514)
FAIR Implementation Profile (FIP)	FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs) are a methodology, developed by GO FAIR, through which a research community expresses its practices and decisions around FAIR. The approach involves a series of questions on how the community makes data and metadata FAIR and what ‘FAIR Enabling Resources’ (FERs) are used. A FER can hence be a tool, software, technology, standard, etc...
Findable	Metadata can (and should) be generous and extensive, including descriptive information about the context, quality and condition, or characteristics of the data. Machine-readable metadata are essential for automatic discovery of datasets and services, so this is an essential component of the FAIRification process. (FAIR Principles - GO FAIR (go-fair.org))
Flexibility	"Flexibility requires taking into account the rapid and often unpredictable changes in information technologies, the characteristics of each research field and the diversity of research systems, legal systems and cultures of each member country. Specific national, social, economic and regulatory implications should be considered when organisations develop research data access arrangements, and when governments develop policies to promote data access and review the implementation of these Principles and Guidelines" (https://www.oecd.org/sti/inno/38500813.pdf)
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). From https://gdpr.eu/what-is-gdpr/ : The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) is the toughest privacy and security law in the world. Though it was drafted and passed by the European Union (EU), it imposes obligations onto organizations anywhere, so long as they target or collect data related to people in the EU. The regulation was put into effect on May 25, 2018. The GDPR will levy harsh fines against those who violate its privacy and security standards, with penalties reaching into the tens of millions of euros. From https://gdpr.eu/article-1-subject-matter-and-objectives-overview/ : This Regulation lays down rules relating to the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and rules relating to the free movement of personal data. This Regulation protects fundamental rights and freedoms of natural persons and in particular their right to the protection of personal data. The free movement of personal data within the Union shall be neither restricted nor prohibited for reasons connected with the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data. (https://gdpr.eu/)

Intellectual property	Intellectual property (IP) refers to creations of the mind, such as inventions; literary and artistic works; designs; and symbols, names and images used in commerce. IP is protected in law by, for example, patents, copyright and trademarks, which enable people to earn recognition or financial benefit from what they invent or create. By striking the right balance between the interests of innovators and the wider public interest, the IP system aims to foster an environment in which creativity and innovation can flourish. (https://www.wipo.int/about-ip/en/)
Legal Interoperability	Legal interoperability is about ensuring that organisations operating under different legal frameworks, policies and strategies are able to work together. This might require that legislation does not block the establishment of European public services within and between Member States and that there are clear agreements about how to deal with differences in legislation across borders, including the option of putting in place new legislation. (EOSC)
Metadata	Metadata are data that describe data. Metadata can (and should) be generous and extensive, including descriptive information about the context, quality and condition, or characteristics of the data. (https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/f2-data-described-rich-metadata/)
(Meta)data schemas	Schemas for (meta)data. "1. The organization or structure for a database. The activity of data modeling leads to a schema. (The plural form is schemata.) The term is used in discussing both relational databases and object-oriented databases. The term sometimes seems to refer to a visualization of a structure and sometimes to a formal text-oriented description. Two common types of database schemata are the star schema and the snowflake schema. 2. A formal expression of an inference rule for artificial intelligence (AI) computing. The expression is a generalized axiom in which specific values or cases are substituted for each symbol in the axiom to derive a specific inference." (https://codata.org/rdm-terminology/schema/)
(Meta)data sharing	Sharing of (meta)data (own definition)
Organisational Interoperability	This refers to the way in which public administrations align their business processes, responsibilities and expectations to achieve commonly agreed and mutually beneficial goals. In practice, organisational interoperability means documenting and integrating or aligning business processes and relevant information exchanged. Organisational interoperability also aims to meet the requirements of the user community by making services available, easily identifiable, accessible and user-focused. (https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/collection/nifo-national-interoperability-framework-observatory/3-interoperability-layers#3.3)

Semantic Interoperability	Semantic interoperability ensures that the precise format and meaning of exchanged data and information is preserved and understood throughout exchanges between parties, in other words 'what is sent is what is understood'. In the EIF, semantic interoperability covers both semantic and syntactic aspects. (https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/collection/nifo-national-interoperability-framework-observatory/glossary/term/semantic-interoperability)
Interoperable	The data usually need to be integrated with other data. In addition, the data need to interoperate with applications or workflows for analysis, storage, and processing. (https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/)
Licenses	A data licence is a legal arrangement between the creator of the data and the end-user, or the place the data will be deposited, specifying what users can do with the data. (https://howtofair.dk/how-to-fair/metadata/#what-are-metadata)
Nanopublication	A nanopublication is the smallest unit of publishable information. This information can be about anything, for example a relation between a gene and a disease or an opinion. Nanopublications are fully expressed in a formal and machine-interpretable way. (https://nanopub.net/)
Open access	Possibility to access and re-use digital research outputs with as few restrictions as possible. Open access refers to both peer-reviewed scientific publications and scientific research data (data underlying publications, other data such as curated but unpublished datasets or raw data) (EU). (https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary ; https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/open-science/open-access_en)
Open data	Data in an open format that can be freely used, re-used and shared by anyone for any purpose. (https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary)
Open science	Approach to the scientific process based on cooperative work and ways of disseminating knowledge, improving accessibility to and re-usability of research outputs by using digital technologies and collaborative tools. Open science is about knowledge as well as data (EU). (https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary ; https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/open-science_en)
Openness	Openness means access on equal terms for the international research community at the lowest possible cost, preferably at no more than the marginal cost of dissemination (extension://elhekieabhbkmcefcoobjddigjcaadp/https://www.oecd.org/science/inno/38500813.pdf)
Other guidelines/frameworks	Refers to any other guidelines' frameworks considered by the different resources (e.g., ECwide and comprehensive) (own definition)
Ownership	Refers to ownership of the data. some resources have specific paragraphs to refer to protection of data ownership (own definition)

Persistent Identifiers	A persistent identifier is a long-lasting reference to a digital object that gives information about that object regardless what happens to it. Developed to address “link rot,” a persistent identifier can be resolved to provide an appropriate representation of an object whether that objects changes its online location or goes offline. SYNONYM. PID (https://codata.org/rdm-terminology/persistent-identifier/)
Policy implementation	Describes the steps for implementation of the policy (own definition)
Policy review	Recurring review (in time) of the data policy, or other applicable policy related to data (own definition)
Preservation	Data preservation not only refers to the long-term storage of data, but also includes ensuring the preservation and maintenance of data, as well as its context, understandability, interpretability, authenticity and integrity. (extension://elhekieabhbkmcefcobjddigjcaadp/ https://symposium22.eoscfuture.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/20221115_EOSC-Symposium-LTDP_v01_00.pdf)
Provenance	A type of historical information or metadata about the origin, location or the source of something, or the history of the ownership or location of an object or resource including digital objects. (https://codata.org/rdm-terminology/provenance/)
Repositories	Repositories preserve, manage, and provide access to many types of digital materials in a variety of formats. Materials in online repositories are curated to enable search, discovery, and reuse. There must be sufficient control for the digital material to be authentic, reliable, accessible and usable on a continuing basis. (https://codata.org/rdm-terminology/repository/)
Research integrity	from the The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity the following principles are defined: "Good research practices are based on fundamental principles of research integrity. They guide researchers in their work as well as in their engagement with the practical, ethical and intellectual challenges inherent in research. These principles are: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reliability in ensuring the quality of research, reflected in the design, the methodology, the analysis and the use of resources. • Honesty in developing, undertaking, reviewing, reporting and communicating research in a transparent, fair, full and unbiased way. • Respect for colleagues, research participants, society, ecosystems, cultural heritage and the environment. • Accountability for the research from idea to publication, for its management and organisation, for training, supervision and mentoring, and for its wider impacts. (https://www.allea.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/05/ALLEA-European-Code-of-Conduct-for-Research-Integrity-2017.pdf)

Researcher Identifiers	For example provided by ORCID: "ORCID provides a persistent digital identifier (an ORCID iD) that you own and control, and that distinguishes you from every other researcher. You can connect your iD with your professional information — affiliations, grants, publications, peer review, and more. You can use your iD to share your information with other systems, ensuring you get recognition for all your contributions, saving you time and hassle, and reducing the risk of errors." ORCID, which stands for Open Researcher and Contributor ID, is a free, unique, persistent identifier (PID) for individuals to use as they engage in research, scholarship, and innovation activities. We provide ORCID to researchers free of charge so that we may realize our vision of connecting all who participate in research, scholarship, and innovation are uniquely identified and connected to their contributions across disciplines, borders, and time" (https://orcid.org/)
Resource accreditation	The GO FAIR Foundation (GFF) has been asked by various sectors to provide FAIR certification for FAIR-related resources. This request has come from a broad range of stakeholders and concerns the widely perceived need for independent third-party criteria and validation of resources with respect to the FAIR Principles. for technical components, domain-relevant standards, FAIR-related training, for FAIR implementation events (e.g., metadata for machines and FAIR Implementation Profile workshops), for people (demonstrating various FAIR-related competencies) and organizations that aspire are committed to FAIR practices. It is believed that certification, when appropriately applied, can be a powerful accelerator of convergence onto widespread FAIR implementations. (Certification - GO FAIR Foundation)
Retention and deletion	Data retention policy: An organization's established protocol for retaining information for operational or regulatory compliance needs. The objectives of a data retention policy are to keep important information for future use or reference, to organize information so it can be searched and accessed at a later date, and to dispose of information that is no longer needed. A data retention policy must consider both the value of data over time, and regulations to which the data may be subject. (Data retention policy - CODATA, The Committee on Data for Science and Technology)
Reusable	The ultimate goal of FAIR is to optimise the reuse of data. To achieve this, metadata and data should be well-described so that they can be replicated and/or combined in different settings. (FAIR Principles - GO FAIR, go-fair.org)
Roles and responsibilities	Describes the roles and responsibility of all individuals and entities concerned with the (activities covered under the) data policy (e.g. legal entities; governments (e.g. EU); organisations, individual researchers, project coordinators; data owners, providers, controllers, users etc. (own definition)
Scope of the policy	The scope of the policy defined the breadth, depth or reach of the data policy; whereas the aim of the policy outlines the aim, purpose of the data policy (own definition)

Sensitive data (businesses)	<p>"In general, the term "sensitive data" is used for any data that could do harm (for example to people, organisations, countries, or ecosystems) if it would be openly available.</p> <p>This can for example be personal or commercial information, but also information such as breeding grounds of endangered species. Any such data must be protected against unauthorized access. What is considered sensitive information is usually regulated by national laws and may differ between countries. You should be cautious when you are dealing with sensitive, or potentially sensitive, information" (https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/sensitive_data#is-your-data-sensitive)</p>
Sensitive data (personal)	<p>"In general, the term "sensitive data" is used for any data that could do harm (for example to people, organisations, countries, or ecosystems) if it would be openly available. This can for example be personal or commercial information, but also information such as breeding grounds of endangered species. Any such data must be protected against unauthorized access. What is considered sensitive information is usually regulated by national laws and may differ between countries. You should be cautious when you are dealing with sensitive, or potentially sensitive, information" (https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/sensitive_data#is-your-data-sensitive)</p>
Service-Level-Agreements	<p>When describing the OpenAIRE Infrastructure Service Level Agreements (SLAs) we refer to the levels of availability, serviceability, performance, operation, or other attributes of the Infrastructure.</p> <p>The level of service is specified as "target" and "minimum," which allows the user of the OpenAIRE Infrastructure to be informed what to expect (the minimum), while providing a measurable (average) target value that shows the level of organization performance. (https://www.openaire.eu/service-level-agreement?highlight=WyJzZXJ2aWNlIiwic2VydmliZSciLCJzZXJ2aWNlIj3MiLCJsZXZlbiClmFncmVlbWVudClmNlcnZpY2UgbGV2ZWwiLCJzZXJ2aWNlIGxldmVslGFncmVlbWVudClmXldmVslGFncmVlbWVudCJd)</p>
Stakeholder	<p>Individuals, groups or organizations that have an interest or share in an undertaking or relationship and its outcome – they may be affected by it, impact or influence it, and in some way be accountable for it. (https://codata.org/rdm-terminology/stakeholder/)</p>
Stakeholder needs	<p>The needs of a stakeholder, with stakeholder being defined as: "an actor [individual or organisation] that can affect, be affected by, or perceive itself to be affected by a decision or activity" (https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary)</p>
Standards	<p>A document that applies collectively to codes, specifications, recommended practices, classifications, test methods, and guides, which have been prepared by a standard developing organization or group, and published in accordance with established procedures. (https://codata.org/rdm-terminology/standard/)</p>

<p>Sustainability</p>	<p>OECD: Due consideration should be given to the sustainability of access to publicly funded research data as a key element of the research infrastructure. This means taking administrative responsibility for the measures to guarantee permanent access to data that have been determined to require long-term retention. This can be a difficult task, given that most research projects, and the public funding provided, have a limited duration, whereas ensuring access to the data produced is a long-term undertaking. Research funding agencies and research institutions, therefore, should consider the long-term preservation of data at the outset of each newproject, and in particular, determine the most appropriate archival facilities for the data."</p> <p>COPCD: Sustainability: verified whether the platform has a clear roadmap planning the future evolutions and whether a specific project and maintenance team is assigned to make the platform responsive to change and user requests. (https://op.europa.eu/nl/publication-detail/-/publication/0af584f7-79a5-11ec-9136-01aa75ed71a1/language-de) (https://www.oecd.org/sti/inno/38500813.pdf)</p>
<p>Transparency</p>	<p>Information on research data and data-producing organisations, documentation on the data and specifications of conditions attached to the use of these data should be internationally available in a transparent way, ideally through the Internet.</p> <p>Lack of visibility of existing research data resources and future data collection poses serious obstacles to access (extension://elhekieabhbkmcefcobjddigjcaadp/https://www.oecd.org/science/inno/38500813.pdf)</p>
<p>Warranty and liability</p>	<p>Refers to warranty and liability in relation to the data (inspired by IPCHEM and JRC paragraphs).</p> <p>JRC: Involves: no obligation to technical support / remedies for the data; no guarantee that the data will be free of errors, accurate or complete; not liable for any damage resulting from using the data; "warranty against infringement of third parties' property rights, or merchantability, integration, satisfactory quality and fitness for a particular purpose (source JRC)." (own definition)</p>